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Pedro Marques

Centre for Economic Geography, School of Planning and Geography, Glamorgan
Building, King Edward VII Avenue, Cardiff, CF10 3WA, UK

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Abstract

Underlying the crisis affecting peripheral European countries is their structural, long-term loss of competitiveness (Hadjimichalis 2011). This paper will focus on the Portuguese case and discuss the institutional constraints that hindered its economy from transitioning towards the production of higher-value added goods and services. It will discuss institutions as the product of a political process laden with power asymmetries, and argue that the dominance of a relatively small community at the heart of economic and political life in Portugal has conditioned the development of the economy as a whole. Using this framework, this paper will then contribute to the literatures on innovation and technological modernisation and argue that alongside a technical process of catching up there is a political process that can enable or constrain development.

Introduction

The debate about the crisis that has engulfed the EU since 2010 has often focused on the topic of public finances and government profligacy (see as an example Economist 2013). There is however an issue which has been less discussed, though it is central to this crisis both economically and politically: the structural loss of competitiveness of peripheral EU countries in relation to core nations, accentuated since the end of the 20th century (Hadjimichalis 2011, Monastiriotis et al. 2013). This paper will discuss in particular the case of Portugal. In line with the argument developed by Hadjimichalis (2011) mostly (but not exclusively) for Greece, it will be argued that to understand the current plight of this nation one must analyse in greater detail the reasons for its long-term loss of competitiveness. As shown in figures 1 and 2, this country experienced a period of catching-up in the 1960s, relative to the OECD average, based on capital investment and the growth of labour productivity (Lopes 2004).

However since 1973, when a sharp rise in oil prices caused a worldwide recession, it has stopped its convergence process, in contrast, for example, with the experience of similarly sized countries in East Asia (Figure 1). This dynamic of arrested development suggests that something ‘went wrong’ in the process of economic modernisation that Portugal started in the 1960s. It will be suggested here that the problem is fundamentally institutional, and that the macroeconomic problems highlighted in discussions of the current crisis (Cafiso 2012) are strongly influenced by how the former function.

This paper will build on the conceptual framework developed by Farole et al. (2011) and Rodríguez-Pose and Storper (2006) which identifies community and society as the two core institutions regulating economic behaviour. As the authors explain,

development depends on the balance between strong yet open communities, underpinned by interpersonal relationships and trust, and effective societal rules that enforce the rule of law and prevent lock-in. It will also draw on insights from political economy, and in particular the work of Acemoglu and Robinson (2012) who draw a distinction between extractive and inclusive institutions to explain why some nations fail to achieve greater prosperity. Both conceptual frameworks stress that institutions, both formal and informal, result from multiple processes of conflict and cooperation, consensus and disagreement. Therefore they reflect the power asymmetries that characterise the interaction between different communities in a society. This is important because in societies where a relatively small group of individuals and organisations have been capable of capturing a disproportionate amount of resources, this is likely to condition the emergence of widespread learning and knowledge sharing which are essential to sustain innovation in the long term. Finally, this paper will place this discussion in the context of a political economy framework, to understand how the Portuguese national institutions relate to the wider economic and political environment.

The next section will develop the theoretical framework that underpins this argument by drawing on institutional economic geography (Farole et al. 2011, Rodríguez-Pose and Storper 2006, Gertler 2010), a critical analysis of Acemoglu and Robinson (2012), and the literatures on technological catch-up (Godinho and Fagerberg 2005) and variegated capitalism (Peck and Theodore 2007). This framework will then be discussed empirically, using the example of Portugal. The final section will be used to suggest some avenues for further theoretical and empirical research.

Institutions, Politics and Development

Institutions have been an important theme in Economic Geography for at least two decades (Scott 2000). Examples of their application can be found in work on innovation, in its multiple guises (Asheim and Coenen 2005; Morgan 1997), or on creativity (Scott 2014), with both strands of literature placing innovation, learning and the socio-economic dynamics that underpin them within a cultural and institutional context (Marques 2011). A different example of how they have been used in this discipline has been the research on decentralisation and regional development (Rodríguez-Pose and Ezcurra 2009, Rodríguez-Pose and Krøijer 2009).

Nonetheless there are occasional calls for a renewed attention to the study of institutions in geography, based on the argument that their existence is often taken as a given, with an acknowledgement that they are important but without a larger effort to explore both their conceptual and empirical dimensions (MacLeod 2001). Gertler (2010) for instance, recently lamented that their role is “still poorly understood or under-appreciated within economic geography” (Gertler 2010 p. 2). Despite the relevance of these and other critiques, it will be suggested in this paper that the issue has not been the lack of attention paid to institutions, but rather the narrow, technocratic way in which they have often been conceptualised by geographers (MacLeod 2001, Tomaney 2014). Institutions have mostly been treated as mere repositories of rules and norms that can be either conducive or obtrusive to knowledge generation and diffusion and to economic development (MacLeod 2001; Tomaney 2014).

This fails to take into account the importance of agency, in particular that which is exercised through political processes, and which has a strong impact on the nature and dynamics of institutions. Recent research by Rodríguez-Pose and Garcilazo (2013) and Rodríguez-Pose and Di-Cataldo (2014) has brought this issue to light, by demonstrating

that in less developed regions more policy investment would not significantly improve performance, due to the low quality of government. In other words, particularly among poorer regions, it is politics and not policy which is blocking further development.

The contributions by Farole et al. (2011) and Rodríguez-Pose and Storper (2006) are a gateway to address these points. They argued that research in the social sciences typically uses community or society as the two key concepts underlying institutional explanations of economic development. The first refers to characteristics of group life, and is normally built on interpersonal networks and bonds among individuals. These ties are regulated by what could otherwise be called informal institutions (Pike et al. 2006), such as norms, traditions or social conventions. Communities have the advantage of lowering transaction costs among their members through reciprocal trust but also through the establishment of enforcement mechanisms. Importantly, access to communities tends to involve long-term commitments, the acquisition of specific and complex knowledge and potentially a certain level of pecuniary and emotional investment (Farole et al 2011, Rodríguez-Pose and Storper (2006).

Society refers to the formal institutions that operate on wider spatio-temporal scales. Relationships built under societal rules are relatively anonymous and (ideally) transparent, and they follow a set of codified rules. In contrast to communities, the enforcement of these rules is expensive and time consuming, both because they have to be learned formally and because penalties involve complex individual punishment mechanisms (Farole et al 2011, Rodríguez-Pose and Storper 2006). Despite the assumption that societies operate on larger geographical scales than communities, this is not necessarily the case. A community may extend for example to the level of a nation-state (the German community) which is larger than the society of a smaller country (the

Portuguese society); also communities are not necessarily local, as demonstrated by research on communities of practice (Faulconbridge 2007). There is nonetheless a distinct geography to both concepts, though what it is will depend on the object and subject of analysis.

Even though communities have often been identified as crucial for economic development, for example in the previously cited research on innovation or in research on social capital (Putnam et al. 1993), they can also hinder it by reinforcing rent-seeking, clientelism and nepotism (see as an example Safford 2009). Because of this, bridging mechanisms are necessary, to encourage inter-group mobility and prevent excessive closure. Societal rules by themselves are equally not enough to ensure prosperity, both because of the high costs involved in their enforcement (time and financial costs) but also because they can strongly be affected by the agendas of interest groups. However more important than understanding them as separate entities, the key question is how they influence each other. This interdependence has implications for outcomes in specific geo-historical contexts, since different combinations of strong or weak societies and communities will generate a different set of incentives and rules that can either constrain or promote innovation and economic development. Their interdependence also has implications for the evolutionary trajectories of regions or countries, because these trajectories are likely to be influenced (or be followed) by variations in their relative strength and quality (Rodríguez-Pose and Storper 2006).

There are several areas of research within this topic that would merit further analysis. In the context of this paper, the area that will be explored conceptually and empirically is how countries can get locked-into a sub-optimal combination of strong, closed communities and weak societal rules, and the impact of this lock-in on innovation and

economic development. To explore this theme fully, it is necessary to have a good understanding of political dynamics, because it is in this arena that different communities (or interest groups) meet and influence societal rules (Sabatier 2007), which in turn have a recursive effect on the internal dynamics of communities (by for example reinforcing rent-seeking and thereby contributing to further community closure).

The work of Acemoglu and Robinson (2012) and in particular their distinction between inclusive and extractive institutions, can help illuminate the importance of these dynamics. This framework offers a simple tool to understand how institutions and economic development are strongly influenced by politics and power asymmetries. As the authors state “while economic institutions are critical for determining whether a country is poor or prosperous, it is politics and political institutions that determine which economic institutions a country has” (p. 43). Also, they demonstrate empirically and conceptually that there is no imperative for societies to progress towards fairer institutions that can promote widespread economic growth and the wellbeing of its citizens (Acemoglu and Robinson 2012). This is because those who control politics and political institutions may benefit from the opposite. Importantly, these strong power asymmetries can remain in place even in democracies, through mechanisms that prevent the emergence of an organised challenge to entrenched power.

As can be inferred by their names, inclusive institutions are those that encourage a large number of people to participate in economic activities by giving them the opportunity to develop their skills, talents and interests. To have inclusive institutions a country should be capable of securing private property, must offer an unbiased system of law, provide public services that create opportunities for the majority of the population, allow the creation of new businesses and give individuals the freedom to choose their careers

(Acemoglu and Robinson 2012). In contrast, extractive institutions deny these rights and are instead “designed to extract incomes and wealth from one subset of society to benefit a different subset” (Acemoglu and Robinson 2012 p. 76). The authors also stress that institutions are path-dependent, which means that they are the product of long-term evolution and tend to be self-reinforcing. And finally they argue that for inclusive institutions to work properly, countries should have a significant degree of centralised power, to avoid fragmentation and guarantee an equal application of the law.

The framework developed by Acemoglu and Robinson (2012) does not have a clear definition of community. They refer to interest groups, or power elites, without defining them clearly and without exploring their internal dynamics. Using the concepts presented by Farole et al. (2011), it could be argued that extractive institutions prevail in a context of strong and closed communities (or at the extreme, *one* closed community). At the same time, the power of these communities is reinforced by the presence of weak societal rules, or alternatively strong rules biased towards their interests, which are bound to be a product of the action of those same communities and at the same time a causal mechanism allowing them to remain in a privileged position.

Our understanding of these processes can also be aided by the work of Allen (2003, 2004) on power and geography. As the author stressed, power is both the result of the potential that each institution has to exercise it (for example as the result of its size, or its legal right to enforce rules) and its capacity to mobilise resources in order to effectively accomplish its goals. Therefore, power asymmetries have to be constantly reinforced by the actions of agents, both those that are dominant and those that are dominated. This is important because it points to the evolutionary nature of the inclusiveness or exclusiveness of institutions, since both can be either reinforced or

challenged as a result of endogenous and exogenous processes. It also counteracts the tendency to view power as a deterministic force, when in fact its exercise is constantly being challenged through a variety of mechanisms (Hobson and Seabrooke 2007).

Power is a fluid concept that can assume different modalities (charisma, coercion, leadership or intimidation) and that is sensitive to resistance (active or passive) and to attrition caused by geographical distance (Allen 2003, 2004).

The framework of Acemoglu and Robinson (2012) exhibits several other important shortcomings that could be addressed by cross-fertilisation with economic geography. First, their simplistic binary distinction between inclusive and exclusive institutions does not acknowledge shifts in time within a particular society, such as the recent rise in inequality in advanced democracies and its strong negative effects on opportunity and inclusiveness (Wilkinson and Pickett 2010, Piketty 2014). Their approach also does not take into account variation in inclusiveness within a country, for example between people of different ethnicities or genders. This is important, because it means that even in a context of formal inclusiveness (where for example the law forbids discrimination) powerful social conventions can have a significant impact on who benefits from existing institutions (WEF 2013). Thirdly, and of specific interest to geographers, they do not mention that the inclusiveness of institutions has a geographical dimension, which is patent in the difference of opportunities that people encounter depending on where they live (see as an example Dorling 2005).

The value of their approach lies instead on the straightforward arguments regarding the role of political processes in influencing institutions, which have been absent from several strands of literature in economic geography (Tomaney 2014). Of equal relevance, is their demonstration that institutions do not evolve along a teleological path

towards increasing quality and as a consequence towards promoting widespread prosperity. In the article by Rodríguez-Pose and Storper (2006) there are similar assumptions, though the trajectories of change identified by them (which revolve around changes in the relative strength and power of communities and societies vis a vis each other) have not been tested empirically to the same extent than the concepts of Acemoglu and Robinson (2012 – see also Acemoglu et al. 2005).

Institutions, innovation and the political economy of development

The framework for institutional analysis presented in the previous paragraphs can contribute to a better understanding of how institutions enable or constrain innovation and technological modernisation, which are the engines that allow countries and regions to catch-up economically. The literature on innovation has demonstrated that innovative agglomerations are usually supported by strong social dynamics, based on the production and circulation of knowledge (Marques 2011). The presence of strong and open communities would be an essential mechanism to achieve this, by reducing transaction costs at the micro-level and facilitating the processes of “searching, finding and securing complex batches of appropriately matched resources” (Farole et al. 2011, pp. 62) that enable technological progress.

The micro-level of community interacts with the societal level, because it is at this scale that formal rules are determined. These rules influence the existence of widespread opportunities, through an investment in education in skills for example, or by providing a stable legal basis that encourages entrepreneurialism (Rodríguez-Pose and Storper 2006). On the other hand, when the institutional environment is more unbalanced (in terms of the relationship between community and society), or said in other words, where extractive institutions prevail, the tendency will be for the diversion of resources

towards a small number of agents and firms (Acemoglu and Robinson 2011), with consequences for the rest of the economy.

Beyond the endogenous characteristics of regions and nations, it is also necessary to acknowledge the relational nature of development, to consider how a region or nation's economic prospects are influenced by their position in the "spatial circuits of production, circulation, consumption and regulation" (MacKinnon 2009 pp 137). Of particular relevance to this paper, is the fact that economic specialisations tend to occur over long periods of time and generate strong path-dependencies (Pike et al 2006). It cannot therefore be ignored that, for example, countries on the European periphery are likely to encounter obstacles to their technological modernisation, due to their inclusion in a large territorial unit (the EU) where other nations have a significant advantage in terms of their specialisation in high value-added goods and services (Hadjimichalis 2011).

Therefore, while empirically this paper relies on the analysis of one particular nation-state, it does not ignore the multi-scalar nature of development, especially in the context of deepening international economic integration. The institutions that allow for the coordination of economic activity within a country are both a product of its internal characteristics and their relation with external processes, which create a set of opportunities and constraints and that help explain why certain institutional arrangements predominate in any given geo-historical context (Peck and Theodore 2007, Peck and Zhang 2013). Highlighting this point allows one to avoid explanations that rely entirely on internal dynamics (internal to the region or the nation) and that often lead to 'blame the victim' type approaches, which put all the onus of underdevelopment on those that have suffered the most with economic restructuring.

Summarising, in the previous paragraphs it has been suggested that a clearer understanding of institutions, and how they are moulded by politics and power, is important to understand better the processes and dynamics of economic growth. This framework will now be applied to discuss an empirical example: the structural loss of economic competitiveness in Portugal. Some of this discussion would also be useful to the three other countries of Southern Europe (Spain, Italy and Greece) which have to a certain extent experienced similar processes. The empirical results are based on an analysis of secondary sources, though the development of this argument is informed by case study research that the author has conducted in recent years (REFERENCES TO BE INCLUDED LATER).

Portugal – the economic and institutional context

Building on the theoretical framework developed in the previous paragraphs, it will be argued that Portugal has failed to restructure its economy towards the production of high value-added goods and services partly due to an unbalance in its institutions. This unbalance is characterised by the presence of a relatively closed community of businesspeople and top politicians, as documented in Costa *et al.* (2010), alongside other smaller communities that represent less competitive firms and sectors, with few opportunities for inter-group mobility. At the societal level, the country is characterised by a dysfunctional justice system (Santos 2009), and low quality of governance (Rodríguez-Pose and Di-Cataldo 2014), meaning that the mechanisms that exist (or should exist) to promote transparency and equality towards the law are not properly enforced (Santos 2009). The interaction between these institutional dimensions is arguably what explains why Portugal has one of the highest levels of rent-seeking in Europe, together with Greece and Italy (Angelopoulos et al. 2009) and is among the

most unequal developed countries in the world (Wilkinson and Pickett 2010). The impact of this context, which could be characterised as one dominated by extractive institutions, has been that the fruits of economic development have not been shared and explored widely among its population. This in turn has hindered innovation, collaboration and growth.

It is important to emphasise that this argument does not invalidate other explanations for slow productivity growth, based on an analysis of technological modernisation (Godinho and Fagerberg 2005). As will be shown in the following paragraphs, both lines of analysis should instead be understood as interdependent. Also, this does not suggest that this country's recent experience can be detached from the structural problems that resulted from it joining the Euro (Hadjimichalis 2011), but instead that those problems were made worse due to the internal characteristics of its institutional system.

Figures 1 and 2 provide the overall picture for Portugal's economic trajectory between 1950 and 2013. Between 1961 and 1973, the country witnessed a period of economic convergence with wealthier nations, measured in terms of labour productivity (Figure 1). Since then it has lived in a situation of 'arrested development', with brief periods of convergence and divergence, but without ever returning to its highest relative position, achieved in 1973 (70% of the OECD average). Measured in terms of GDP per capita, it has performed slightly better, with convergence lasting until the early 2000s, as a result of a growing active population.

Multiple indexes confirm its economy's low performance in comparison with more developed countries. Portugal as a whole is characterised as a moderate innovator in the context of the EU, despite recent improvements, (Hollanders and Es-Sadki 2014), with

one region classified as an innovation follower (Lisbon, where the capital city is located), five as moderate innovators and one as a modest innovator (Algarve, dominated by the tourist sector) (Hollanders et al. 2014). In the Global Competitiveness Report (2014) its strongest performance is in infrastructure (17th in the world), health and primary education (24th) and higher education and training (24th). On the other hand, its worst performance is in the macroeconomic environment (128th), financial market development (104th) and labour market efficiency (83rd). Regarding the quality of its institutional environment, it occupies the position 41 in the global competitiveness index. In the European Quality of Government Index, the country as a whole is ranked at the bottom of Western Europe.

(Figures 1 and 2 about here)

It is however important to go beyond the national aggregate data in order to get a more nuanced understanding of its economy. In particular, data on the Portuguese business structure paints the picture of an economy with significant asymmetries. Figures 3 and 4 show that in Portugal small firms with 9 or less employees account for a significantly higher proportion of total employment than in the EU (27 countries) and particularly in comparison to the 14 wealthiest EU countries (measured in terms of GDP per capita). Crucially, the second figure shows that these small firms contribute to less than 25% of total value added, which indicates that even though large Portuguese firms have similar performances to those in other countries (measured in terms of the relationship between contribution to employment and value added), small firms are significantly less productive.

Table 1 helps explain this lack of competitiveness. It shows the contribution of each economic sector to total value added in Portugal and in the EU (15). The different

shadings show that the sectors in Portugal that contribute more to total value added in comparison with the value for the EU (15) are of two sorts: the first includes sectors such as textiles, retail and tourism, where SMEs represent a large share of the business population. They are mostly labour intensive, exposed to high competition from countries with lower factor costs and have limited opportunities for innovation. Case studies of these sectors show that even though there are a few examples of firms investing in innovation and high value added products, most still rely on labour costs that are comparatively lower in an European context (Vale and Caldeira 2007).

(Figures 3 and 4 about here)

The second group of sectors includes electricity, telecommunications, air transport and financial services. As will be discussed in the next section, these sectors of activity have been in different ways protected by the government and remain concentrated in firms with a long-term presence in the Portuguese economy (see table 2). Finally this table also shows that public administration and education make a higher than average contribution to value added. According to Mateus (2006) this is because state expansion at the end of the 1990s was the only way to disguise what was already a clear drop in economic competitiveness.

(Table 1 about here)

Politics and institutions – historical evolution

Following the contextualisation of the Portuguese economy, it is now necessary to explore the institutional origins of the economic asymmetries identified, starting with the dictatorship that ruled Portugal between 1933 and 1974. During this period corporatism was an essential component of the stability of the regime, similarly to what

happened in Italy under Mussolini or Spain under Franco (Rosas 2013). Rhetorically, political leaders argued that they wanted to ensure the autonomy of the economic sphere, with the public sector being called to this arena merely as a regulator. In reality, the government intervened strongly in the economy, shielding the most important sectors from competition by attributing monopolies or oligopolies to privately owned firms, under a policy called industrial conditioning, or by favouring them through trade tariffs (Costa et al. 2010, Garrido and Rosas 2012). It also created a host of regulatory institutions that tightly controlled business interaction (by stipulating basic prices for instance) and limited workers' rights, in order to guarantee steady returns on investment, which was seen as necessary in a country dominated by rent-seeking and uncompetitive business interests (Rosas 2013). . The result was that by 1960 Portugal remained, according to indicators on economic and social development, a developing country (Pintado 2002).

After joining the European Free Trade Agreement (EFTA) in 1960 and signing the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) in 1961, Portugal lived through a twelve year period of growth, as mentioned previously in this paper (Lopes 2004 and figures 1 and 2). Most of the new firms in textiles, shoemaking and glassmaking established themselves away from the capital city, in the north and centre of Portugal, where there was traditionally a stronger entrepreneurial culture (Salgueiro, 1992; Valério and Mata 1994). Distance from the centre of power, and the fact that they mostly remained small, granted these firms a certain amount of independence (see as an example the oral histories collected about the moulds industry in Beira and Gomes 2007).

After a period of turbulence in 1974-75, following the installation of democracy, when banks and large firms were nationalised, and land was distributed under an agrarian reform, the country entered a period of ‘normalisation’, which eventually led to the reprivatisation of some public companies and the return of land to their previous owners. This ‘normalisation’ happened in a context of strong path-dependencies, which led to a renewed alliance between government and a few core firms (some still owned by the state, others privatised or returned to their previous owners), and the return of several individuals that had been central in the community that sustained the previous regime. This point has been demonstrated by Costa et al. (2010) who identified the main economic dynasties in the Portuguese economy, stretching to the beginning of the 20th century. Coming from sectors such as tobacco plantation, trade, finance and real estate, there are a small number of families that remain at the core of the Portuguese economy, since the middle of the 19th century (the family surnames are Burney, Mayer, Ulrich, Mello and Espírito Santo Silva). Others will join later, in particular the Champallimaud family, with investments also in the financial sector plus industrial activities such as cement. According to Costa et al. (2010) the most remarkable aspects of these families are their resilience and their tendency to promote marriage between their descendants. They were also overwhelmingly concentrated in the Lisbon suburbs of Estoril, Sintra and Cascais. As the authors showed it is possible to trace their presence to some of the biggest Portuguese firms in 2010.

Table 2 provides some current data to illustrate this point. It shows the 20 companies with the highest value in the Portuguese stock market in June 2014 and highlights how their size is a product of the economic and political history of this country. The maintenance of a relatively closed community at the helm of the Portuguese economy happened however through different mechanisms than those used during the

dictatorship. With the disappearance of the corporatist state, the three main mechanisms became: 1) the direct intervention of the state, either through firm ownership, or through the creation of monopolies and oligopolies in core sectors (see table 2). The public ownership of firms supplying core goods and services (such as telecommunications, energy or postal services) is not exclusive to the Portuguese case. What is more striking is that when new technologies and areas of activity arose, the tendency to restrict competition and privilege incumbent corporations remained. For example, until recently only three companies had the right to supply mobile phone communications in Portugal (Vodafone, Sonae and PT; the latter two merged recently their mobile phone and internet divisions). Also in the implementation of new digital terrestrial television, research has suggested that PT was favoured by the agency responsible for regulating this market in Portugal (Denicoli 2012); in yet another example, Galp Energia retains a monopoly for refining oil in Portugal.

The second mechanism has been the emergence of 2) an intricate web of cross-shareholding between main corporations and financial institutions, (a trait common to other Southern European Countries - Barber 2013), as explained in great detail in Costa et al. (2010). The impact of this mechanism was highlighted recently, when in October 2014 the Espírito Santo Group (ESG – see table 2) declared bankruptcy after accumulating debts of over five billion Euro. According to a journalistic investigation (Ferreira 2014a, 2014b), before its demise the CEO of the group used his personal connections to get Portugal Telecom (PT) to inject nearly one billion Euro in the holding, contradicting the latter's previous decision to withdraw its investments from the ESG. The impact was so significant that PT's share prices fell to their lowest historical share price, due to their exposure to the group. This investigation also

demonstrated the bank's connections to many other large Portuguese corporations through networks of personal affinity, such as Semapa (see table 2).

Another example is given by Banco Comercial Português (Table 2), the biggest Portuguese private bank. One of this bank's major strategic shareholder is the Jose Mello Group (a traditional family identified in previous paragraphs), who also has positions in Brisa (a formerly state owned company, responsible for building and managing motorways). This group also owns CUF, a traditional industrial conglomerate previously protected by the industrial conditioning laws, and has an important presence in the private health sector.

The third and final mechanism is 3) the circulation of key individuals between business and politics. Through an analysis of the professional paths of 115 individuals who were at some point government officials since 1974, Costa et al. (2010) were able to identify a network that includes virtually all major Portuguese corporations. It shows that it is normal practice for politicians to leave government directly to these corporations, occasionally returning to the public sphere at a later stage. A famous example was given by Ferreira do Amaral, who, as a Government Minister, negotiated a public private partnership with Lusoponte which according to the Portuguese Audit Court benefited the company at the expense of the public purse (De Lemos et al. 2004). At a later date the same individual became the President of Lusoponte. A different example can be found in the investigation of Ferreira (2014a, 2014b) on the unravelling of the ESG group. According to the author, in 2004 the two individuals responsible for drafting the electoral programmes for the two main political parties (the centre right PSD and the centre left PS) worked in BESI, the investment bank owned by ESG. They would

discuss their ideas in the corridors of the company, and according to Ferreira, ESG benefited from this proximity (Ferreira 2014a, 2014b).

From an analytical point of view, it could be argued that through the 20th century, and particularly during the dictatorship, a core business community established itself in Portugal, covering a variety of key sectors. This community thrived in a context of strong (authoritarian) societal rules, because it was an important pillar for the stability of the regime (Rosas 2013). With democracy, after a brief period of political turmoil, societal rules became less rigid. In fact, the Portuguese justice system has often been criticised for its dysfunctions, which tend to benefit those with resources that can deal with its delays and complex procedures (Santos 2009). In this context this closed-knit community reorganised itself and found ways to remain influential, even though the Portuguese economy became more open. The power exercised by this community is less based on coercion and formal rules (though the latter still count, as seen by the several monopolies and oligopolies that remain), but more based on proximity to the centres of power, relative closeness to outsiders and the co-optation of key political figures.

Institutions and development in Portugal

The characteristics of the Portuguese economy described in the previous section are not necessarily exclusive to this country. Why then are these elements more important in this context? First of all, having an ‘oversized sector’ (as measured in table 1), which receives some type of preferential treatment from the state is not necessarily negative, if those sectors contribute to productivity increases and innovation in the economy as a whole. This is what happened in the developmental states of East Asia, where an investment in automobiles (Japan) and electronics (Singapore or Taiwan) had knock-on effects not only on suppliers, but also in the financial sector, education and training

systems and ultimately on governance mechanisms (Godinho and Fagerberg 2005). This is because despite initial state protection, large firms in these countries operate in capital intensive, highly competitive sectors, where innovation (particularly in organisational practices) was crucial to sustain growth.

In the Portuguese case, the large firms supported by the state operate in sectors with limited competition, either because they are natural monopolies, according to the definition by Stiglitz (2003), where due to very high entry barriers competition tends to be limited (this is the case for electricity or postal services); because their markets are highly regulated and/or intertwined with government activity such as finance; or because there was a deliberate decision to restrict competition (as demonstrated in table 2 and previously in this paper). For these reasons they did not have the same pull effect that core firms had for example in East Asia.

Also, since some of these firms operate in highly regulated markets, their prices (and as a result their profits) are dependent on decisions by government agencies, which in the Portuguese case have occasionally benefited the corporation at the expense of the consumer. The high cost of electricity and natural gas for instance, is an example of costs being imposed on the rest of the economy to support previously state owned companies (see table 3). Recently a report by the current national Government argued that a deal established by the previous government with Galp Energia (Table 2), had allowed the company to gain excess profits of around 500 million EUR between 2006 and 2012 (Ferreira 2014c). This deal was done at a time when Galp had a monopoly in the distribution of natural gas and where therefore the regulator would need to intervene to prevent abuses of power.

A different example was the significant investment in motorways over the past three decades. It led Portugal to have the highest number of kilometres of motorway in relation to its GDP per capita (Crescenzi and Rodríguez-Pose 2012). As shown by Rodríguez-Pose and Fratesi (2004) these investments did not have a significant impact on economic growth. This is important because at least two large Portuguese firms have benefited from this construction (Mota-Engil and Brisa). Both benefit from their economic and political connections, as described in previous paragraphs, which would indicate that at least part of the decision to invest in this type of infrastructure was made to sustain these large corporations, rather than because of their economic return.

These costs and investments may not relate explicitly to innovation and technological modernisation, but they are an opportunity cost with consequences for the rest of the economy, especially in a relatively small and poorer country (in the EU context) such as Portugal. Considering for example the historically low levels of investment in science (which only improved recently - Hollanders and Es-Sadki 2014) or the below than average educational attainment of its population (Figure 5), there are grounds to claim that successive Portuguese governments did not always invest their resources in ways that would promote more widespread growth through inclusiveness and innovation.

Notwithstanding the argument that has been developed so far in this paper, it is necessary to ask the counterfactual question: could Portugal have developed without the close alliance between business and politics identified in previous paragraphs? A multi-scalar approach (Peck and Theodore 2007) could indicate that considering its structural economic disadvantage in relation to the core EU economies, the limited size of its internal market, and its lack of natural resources, this country would always struggle to alter significantly its position in the wider European pattern of economic specialisation. From this perspective, maintaining a strong alliance with key sectors, such as finance,

energy, air transport and telecommunications, was the only solution to avoid these activities from being dominated by foreign firms. This domination would probably have meant that all high-end corporate functions would have left for the main EU capital cities, further reinforcing Portugal's specialisation in low value-added activities.

A comparison with other countries of a similar size (such as those in figures 1 and 2) that have gone through significant economic restructuring over the past few decades can throw some light on this issue. In the European context, excluding countries that have for a long time been integrated with the major European economies (such as the Netherlands or Denmark), only Ireland has achieved significantly better growth results. However it is unlikely that Portugal could have benefited from the same level of FDI, which was to a certain extent facilitated by the Irish-American diaspora and the fact that Ireland and the USA share the same native language (Pike et al. 2006). In contrast to the Irish experience, the new Central and Eastern European EU members, some with similar population sizes, appear to be specialising as branch-plant economies, which poses a serious threat to their long-term economic prospects. Similarly to Portugal (or to Greece as described by Hadjimichalis 2011), they might struggle to leverage this FDI to stimulate innovation and endogenous growth. Among East Asian countries, there are other relevant factors that distinguish their path. South Korea and especially Japan had significantly larger internal markets on which their firms could rely to achieve critical mass before internationalising. Additionally, Singapore, Taiwan or Hong Kong have benefited both from their privileged connections to the UK or the USA and their role in facilitating access to China and its huge labour market resources (Meyer et al. 2009, Pike et al 2006).

However, though this approach throws up some important questions, it is not entirely unproblematic. If IEG has often relied on isolating what happens inside a region or

nation from the wider context, there is an alternative danger of becoming excessively deterministic, with all examples that do not comply with the norm being dismissed as merely a new element in an unchanging system. When comparing national experiences, there is a constant tension between drawing comparisons on a more superficial level (such as differences in main sectors of specialisation), or delving deeper into the specific economic and political conditions that facilitated development. When opting for the latter, the detail may be used to suggest incomparability rather than to identify useful lessons.

Part of the problem is that development trajectories can only be known after the fact, which means that it is impossible to tell precisely what would have happened had things been different. For this reason, it is argued here that even though Portugal lacked some of the elements that allowed similarly sized countries to develop, it does not mean that a stronger convergence process would have been impossible, under a different political and economic set of institutions. While accepting that this is purely speculative, if these institutions had prevented the accumulation of so many resources in a few core firms, dominated by a small number of actors and operating in sectors with limited competition, and had invested instead in the education of the wider population for example, or in supporting the emergence of new sectors of activity (or at least in facilitating their emergence) or in improving the transparency and efficiency of the justice system, the country could potentially have achieved a different set of results.

Conclusions

The objective in this paper has been to demonstrate that there is a link between the fundamentals of the political process, the way it is both cause and consequence of a particular institutional environment (characterised by different combinations of

community and society and their relative strength and openness), and the way it constrains the behaviour of individuals and organisations. The case of Portugal was used as an example, to argue that the reason why its economy has failed to restructure towards the production of high-value added goods and services is partly due to an institutional imbalance. This imbalance leads to a concentration of resources in a small number of well-connected firms and organisations and to an environment that does not encourage wide learning and experimentation in the economy.

The framework advanced by Farole et al. (2011) and Rodríguez-Pose and Storper (2006), and the contributions of Acemoglu and Robinson (2012) provided important intellectual guidance, helping to bring greater clarity to the definition of institutions and to tease out their various economic, political and social dimensions. However this paper has also highlighted some limitation in these literatures, which will need to be further developed in the future. The first regards the identification of community boundaries. In this case study, the community that is said to dominate the Portuguese institutional and economic environment, is relatively fluid and difficult to delimit. Even though there is a spatial association to the suburbs of Lisbon from which the traditional Portuguese families emerge, this spatial dimension has lost some of its importance as the community grew and incorporated new actors.

An alternative way to define this community would be through the notion of different types of proximity, in a similar vein to what Boschma (2005) argued in the context of innovation. For example personal proximity, which results from being directly connected through family ties, or indirectly by developing close relationships through professional or political affinities. A second type would be proximity to centres of power, measured in terms of the depth of the relationships with other core private or

public organisations. In the Portuguese context this depth would be measured in terms of participation in cross-shareholding arrangements, the extent to which an organisation benefits from state protection, and the presence and importance of an organisation in the network that maps the circulation of key politicians through business and the state. This would allow for an identification of communities that cut across geographical and sectoral boundaries but still maintain a certain level of cohesiveness.

In addition, the concepts of capacity trust and emotive trust, coupled with the notion of multiple rationalities (Ettlinger 2003), can help to explain why individuals develop strong interpersonal connections for reasons other than narrow economic interests.

Capacity trust refers to a belief that someone is capable of performing a certain task, while emotive trust is about personal feelings towards other human beings. Multiple rationalities points to the many logics subjacent to individual behaviour, including economic, political or social. Communities are formed and maintained to serve these various logics, which explains their relative openness or closure, depending on their prevailing logic. It also helps to understand the function of spatial concentration, particularly in situations where emotive trust is a cornerstone of interpersonal links, because physical proximity helps to build and maintain strong human connections.

Importantly, Ettlinger (2003) demonstrates that an overlap in networks is not sufficient to elicit inter-group mobility. This overlap needs to be underpinned by the intent to actively engage with different communities, which can be avoided through network-closure and restricting access. By integrating these concepts, the concept of community as developed by Farole et al (2011) would become theoretically more robust and easier to operationalise empirically.

The second limitation relates to trajectories of institutional change. Rodríguez-Pose and Storper (2006) identified several possible trajectories, but described them mostly on a conceptual level without empirical testing. On the other hand, Acemoglu and Robinson (2012) tend to rely on long-term evolution to explain institutional outcomes. For example their explanation for the different developmental paths of North and Latin America lies on colonial property right and its impact on the inclusiveness of institutions in the present. As argued previously in this paper this ignores changes in inclusiveness which are currently taking place; but it also provides limited guidance on how to study institutional change during shorter time spans, or on what type of actions could lead to institutional change. The case- study examined in this paper would indicate that acting at the societal level, by creating a fairer set of rules and better enforcement mechanisms, could potentially unlock the relations of privilege established within a small, closed community. Different examples will have to be discussed in future research, particularly ones where it is strong societal rules, in the context of weak and poorly organised communities, which are responsible for sub-optimal institutional outcomes.

Finally this paper also highlights some implications for the economic geography literature. In the same way that the multi-scalar approach of Peck and Theodore (2007) was introduced to shed light on the relation between national institutions and the international political economy, the empirical discussion in the previous section poses serious questions about the tendency to view regions in isolation of their national environment. In particular the literature on innovation, with its emphasis on micro or meso-level dynamics (Marques 2011), often fails to link the socio-dynamics that exist in a particular territory with the formal or informal institutional settings that emerge at the national level. This is important because several underlying dimensions of innovation

(such as education, science, or labour market regulation), as well as other economic variables such as public investment strategies, are mostly decided at the national level. A narrow focus on sub-national processes risks ignoring an important set of mechanisms that influence where innovation is happening, which sectors and actors are included in it, and whether it contributes to overall growth or merely to reinforce the competitiveness of incumbent firms.

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Figure 1 – Labour productivity* in Portugal and other countries between 1950 and 2013 as a percentage of the OECD average**

* measured as GDP per person employed

** Excluding 5 countries due to missing data points in some years (Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Slovak Republic, Slovenia)

Source: Total Economy Database (The Conference Board 2014)

Figure 2 – GDP per capita in Portugal and other countries between 1950 and 2013 as a percentage of the OECD average*

* Excluding 5 countries due to missing data points in some years (Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Slovak Republic, Slovenia)

Source: Total Economy Database (The Conference Board 2014)

Figure 3 - Contribution of firms to total employment according to their size group in 2010

Source: author's calculation based on Eurostat (2014)

Figure 4 - Contribution of firms to total value added at factor cost according to their size group in 2010

Source: author's calculation based on Eurostat (2014)

Table 1 – Contribution of individual sectors to total gross value added in Portugal and in EU (15) in 2010 (%)

	EU (15)	Portugal
Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities	1,3	1,6
Forestry and logging	0,2	0,4
Fishing and aquaculture	0,1	0,3
Mining and quarrying	0,6	0,5
Manufacture of food products; beverages and tobacco products	1,9	2,1
Manufacture of textiles, wearing apparel, leather and related products	0,6	2,0
Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of articles of straw and plaiting materials	0,3	0,5
Manufacture of paper and paper products	0,4	0,6
Printing and reproduction of recorded media	0,3	0,3
Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products	0,2	0,4
Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products	1,1	0,5
Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	0,7	0,3
Manufacture of rubber and plastic products	0,7	0,6
Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products	0,6	1,0
Manufacture of basic metals	0,6	0,2
Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment	1,5	1,5
Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products	0,7	0,5
Manufacture of electrical equipment	0,8	0,5
Manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c.	1,7	0,4
Manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	1,2	0,7
Manufacture of other transport equipment	0,4	0,1
Manufacture of furniture; other manufacturing	0,7	0,6

Table 1 (continued) – Contribution of individual sectors to total gross value added in Portugal and in EU (15) in 2010 (%)

	EU (15)	Portugal
Repair and installation of machinery and equipment	0,7	0,5
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	2,2	2,7
Water collection, treatment and supply	0,3	0,4
Sewerage, waste management, remediation activities	0,7	0,7
Construction	6,1	6,3
Wholesale and retail trade and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	1,4	1,4
Wholesale trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	5,4	5,7
Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	4,2	6,6
Land transport and transport via pipelines	2,3	1,9
Water transport	0,3	0,1
Air transport	0,2	0,7
Warehousing and support activities for transportation	1,5	1,8
Postal and courier activities	0,4	0,4
Accommodation and food service activities	3,2	5,0
Publishing activities	0,6	0,3
Motion picture, video, television programme production; programming and broadcasting activities	0,6	0,3
Telecommunications	1,6	2,0
Computer programming, consultancy, and information service activities	1,9	1,0
Financial service activities, except insurance and pension funding	4,3	5,2
Insurance, reinsurance and pension funding, except compulsory social security	0,9	1,2
Activities auxiliary to financial services and insurance activities	0,7	0,5
Real estate activities	10,4	8,5
Imputed rents of owner-occupied dwellings	6,0	5,2

Table 1 (continued) – Contribution of individual sectors to total gross value added in Portugal and in EU (15) in 2010 (%)

	EU (15)	Portugal
Legal and accounting activities; activities of head offices; management consultancy activities	3,1	2,3
Architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis	1,3	0,9
Scientific research and development	0,5	0,4
Advertising and market research	0,5	0,3
Other professional, scientific and technical activities; veterinary activities	0,5	0,2
Rental and leasing activities	1,2	0,6
Employment activities	1,0	0,1
Travel agency, tour operator reservation service and related activities	0,2	0,2
Security and investigation, service and landscape, office administrative and support activities	1,8	1,7
Public administration and defence; compulsory social security	6,9	8,8
Education	5,2	6,8
Human health activities	5,3	4,7
Residential care activities and social work activities without accommodation	2,4	1,4
Creative, arts and entertainment activities; libraries, archives, museums and other cultural activities; gambling and betting activities	0,8	0,3
Sports activities and amusement and recreation activities	0,5	0,5
Activities of membership organisations	0,7	0,3
Repair of computers and personal and household goods	0,2	0,1
Other personal service activities	0,9	0,7
Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods- and services-producing activities of households for own use	0,5	1,0

Source: author's calculation based on Eurostat 2014

Note: The lighter shade of gray indicates which of the two areas has a higher contribution from a particular sector; the darker shade of gray is for sectors where the difference is higher than 0.5

Table 2 - Name of companies listed in the PSI20*, their area of activity and characteristics that make them relevant for this paper

Name of company	Area of activity	Relevance
ALTRI SGPS SA	Paper pulp	Protected by laws of industrial conditioning during dictatorship – nationalised in 1974 and later reprivatised
B.COM.PORTUGUES	Banking	Financial industry – managed until 2005 by Jardim Gonçalves, who left the country in 1974 and was later invited by a member of the Portuguese government to create a new private bank
B.ESPIRITO SANTO	Banking	Financial industry – Part of Espirito Santo Group
BANCO BPI SA	Banking	Financial industry – CEO Fernando Ulrich
BANIF SA	Banking	Financial industry
CTT	Mail, Logistics	Former State owned company responsible for postal services – privatised in 2013
ESFG	Banking	Financial industry – Part of Espirito Santo Group
IMPRESA	Media	Owens one of two private TV open channels, newspapers and other media – CEO Francisco Pinto Balsemão, Prime Minister of Portugal between 1981 and 1983 and member of the National Assembly during the dictatorship between 1969 and 1973 as part of the ‘Liberal Wing’
EDP	Energy	Former State owned company – had monopoly of electricity distribution in Portugal until 2007, when the Iberian (Portugal and Spain) market for energy was created
EDP RENOVAVEIS	Renewable energy	Former State owned company – part of EDP
GALP ENERGIA	Oil and Gas	Former State owned company – continues to have the monopoly of oil refining in Portugal.
J MARTINS SGPS	Food production and retail	Origins date back to business started in 1792 - current Chairman in place since 1968
MOTA ENGIL	Construction	Created in 1946 – President between 2008 and 2013 was a professional politician and former Minister with no previous business experience – manages several motorways through public-private partnerships
PORTUCEL	Paper manufacturing	Protected by laws of industrial conditioning during dictatorship – nationalised in 1974 and later reprivatised
PORTUGAL TELECOM	Telecommunications	Former State owned company – it had monopoly of landline communications until 1999 and had one of three mobile phone licences in Portugal until 2014. The company was accused in 2012 of having been benefited by the Government in the implementation of terrestrial digital television (Denicoli 2012)

Table 2 (continued) - Name of companies listed in the PSI20*, their area of activity and characteristics that make them relevant for this paper

Name of company	Area of activity	Relevance
REN	Energy	Former State owned company - owner of the electricity network in Portugal – also operates on the storage, transportation and regasification of natural gas
SEMAPA	Cement, Paper and pulp, environmental services	Corporation created in 1904 (cement division) – formerly protected by laws of industrial conditioning
SONAE	Holding for group involving retail, ICT services and Commercial Real Estate	Sonae group - created in 1959 and currently managed by son of previous CEO – had until recently one of three mobile phone licences
Teixeira Duarte	Real Estate, Energy, Tourism, Automobile production, etc.	Created in 1921 - family owned company
ZON OPTIMUS	ICTs	Merger between Optimus (previously division of mobile phone and internet for group Sonae), and division of Portugal Telecom operating in the same area

* The PSI20 is an index that includes the 20 biggest organisation trading in the Lisbon stock exchange

SOURCE: Author's own research

Table 3 – Average energy prices between second semester of 2007 and second semester of 2013

Portuguese energy prices as proportion of Euro Area

	Electricity prices		Natural Gas	
	Domestic consumers	Industry consumers	Domestic consumers	Industry consumers
All taxes and levies included	118.43%	101.81%	131.45%	113.36%
Excluding VAT and other recoverable taxes and levies	123.67%	111.17%	139.01%	118.74%
Excluding taxes and levies	113.70%	124.07%	158.20%	127.59%

Portuguese energy prices as proportion of EU (28)

	Electricity prices		Natural Gas	
	Domestic consumers	Industry consumers	Domestic consumers	Industry consumers
All taxes and levies included	124.71%	111.80%	146.53%	119.80%
Excluding VAT and other recoverable taxes and levies	124.71%	111.80%	146.53%	119.80%
Excluding taxes and levies	109.70%	119.33%	160.89%	128.75%

Source: author's calculation based on Eurostat 2014

Note: comparisons are made using only prices for energy bands that Eurostat uses for comparison

Figure 5 - Population, aged 15 to 74 years, by highest level of education attained - 2013

Source: author's calculation based on Eurostat (2014)